

SOUND CULTURE OF SPEECH AS A LANGUAGE BASIS FOR MASTERING SPEECH SKILLS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDHOOD

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Abstract. At preschool age, perception turns into a special cognitive activity with its own tasks and methods of implementation. The younger preschooler is guided by the game goals. One of the leading in the child is visual perception, which allows you to capture all the details of the subject and their relationships. Moreover, the gaze of a child of younger preschool age randomly moves around objects, because the preschooler does not know how to control it. This article delves into Sound culture of speech as a language basis for mastering speech skills in preschool childhood.

Keywords: children's perspective, sound culture, speech development, preschoolers, etc

The perception of children 3-4 years old is controlled and directed by an adult. With proper guidance in the process of various activities, by the age of 4, the child learns to consider objects. Visual-effective thinking arises in connection with the practical actions of younger preschoolers. Children identify the internal properties of objects and their connections in the process of actions with objects. Also, this age is characterized by a visual-figurative form of thinking, in which the child operates with images and ideas, and not with real objects. E. O. Smirnova considers the necessary condition for the formation of this form of thinking "the ability to distinguish between the plan of real objects and the plan of models." All types of activity characteristic of a younger preschooler are of a modeling nature: productive activity, role-playing game. In them, preschoolers create visual models, creating relationships between substitute objects that are perceived in real objects. The third form of mental activity - logical thinking - is only beginning to take shape at a younger preschool age. The child begins to operate with abstract categories and establish relationships that are not represented in a model form. Egocentrism is a feature of the cognitive position of the younger preschooler. It is based on the acceptance of one's position as the only possible one and the inability to take the point of view of another. A child of this age is characterized by egocentric speech, not addressed to the interlocutor, speech for oneself, which is a stage in the development of inner speech - the main means of thinking.

An important role in the mental development of a younger preschooler is played by imagination, which is still closely connected with an object (toy) or action that performs the

function of a support. Children 3-4 years old do not yet know how to create an idea and plan to achieve it. Their intention often appears after the action is performed. It arises spontaneously, under the influence of the situation, and is easily destroyed in the course of its implementation. In children of primary preschool age, only elements of preliminary planning of activities can be observed. The younger preschool age is a qualitatively new stage in the development of speech, which is included in all activities of the child. The intensive development of speech is caused by the emergence of new activities, the expansion of the circle of life connections, the complication of communication and the tasks facing the preschooler. In the game interaction of children of primary preschool age, the researcher notes, non-verbal means of communication predominate (expressive looks, postures, smiles, movements, eye contact). Speech actions are poorly coordinated. Children talk aloud, not paying attention to the words of the partner. The speech consists mainly of simple sentences, its content is connected with a specific situation, with practical activities. The speech of the younger preschooler is involuntary, it is not yet an independent activity and develops depending on the process of communication, but the child is already beginning to master the voluntary regulation of speech.

In the younger preschooler, the pronunciation side of speech is being improved, language means are expanding. At the younger preschool age, the development of attention and memory continues. The amount of attention increases: the child can act with 2-3 objects. Attention becomes more stable and concentrated. In early preschool age, the forms and content of the child's communication change. The possibilities of communication are expanding due to speech development. Now children can communicate about presented objects that are not present at the moment of interaction. Thus, the content of communication becomes extra-situational, going beyond the limits of a certain situation. At the younger preschool age, the communication of children with peers also expands. The child begins to show attention to other children, emotionally respond to their actions, seeks to attract the attention of peers. Along with the development of practical skills, speech, imagination, the contacts of children are multiplied and become more diverse. However, M. I. Lisina notes, younger preschoolers are more adult-oriented, without his participation and assistance they cannot establish cooperation and reach agreement among themselves.

Children of 3-4 years old have a pronounced play motive, as well as an interest in the content and process of new activities for them: design, work, drawing. Cognitive motives are just beginning to develop, as a result of which knowledge is successfully mastered in a didactic game. For a younger preschooler, motives for rewards and punishments are effective, associated with the desire of a child of this age to maintain good relationships with an adult. Moral motives are absent or have little effect. The appearance of new needs, motives, interests in a child of younger preschool age causes the development of his emotions. At the age of 3-4, social emotions and moral

feelings begin to develop. Also, the child masters ways of expressing feelings: with the help of intonation, pantomime, facial expressions. In early preschool age, conditions for moral development are created. In the game, children comprehend the world of human relations, strive to subordinate their behavior to norms and rules. This is how the first moral judgments and assessments are formed, the initial understanding of moral norms arises. Thus, researchers consider the younger preschool age to be sensitive for the development of many mental processes. The change in the social situation of development, the separation of the child from the adult affects the entire inner world of the younger preschooler, his emotional, motivational, social and intellectual sphere of mental development. In a child of primary preschool age, the content of play activities expands, new types of activities appear. They actively develop mental processes: perception, thinking, memory, imagination, speech.

The forms and content of the child's communication with adults and peers are changing. At this age, for the first time, the subordination of motives reveals itself, emotions and moral feelings develop. One of the neoplasms of age is the laying of the personality and image of the I. The sound culture of speech is an integral part of the general speech culture. It includes all aspects of the sound design of words and sounding speech in general: the correct pronunciation of sounds, words, the speed and volume of speech utterance, timbre, rhythm, pauses, logical stress, etc. The necessary conditions for the timely and correct formation of a sound culture of speech are the normal operation of the speech motor and hearing aids, the existence of a full-fledged environmental speech environment. Physical hearing is the ability to hear the sounds of the surrounding world. Speech hearing is the ability of a person to correctly perceive and correctly reproduce sounding speech, that is, to hear, recognize and transmit all the phonological means of a language, comparing them with the established norm. Well-formed speech hearing is a prerequisite for the correct and timely assimilation of sounds, the correct pronunciation of words, mastering speech intonation. It contains the following components: perception of the tempo of speech and voice, pitch hearing, phonemic hearing, rhythmic hearing. Phonemic hearing is the ability to perceive the sounds of speech, phonemes, with the help of which there is a distinction between words that are similar in sound: poppy - varnish - cancer, angle - coal. Its good development makes it possible to form the correct sound pronunciation, distinct and clear pronunciation of words in accordance with the norms of the literary language. The formation of phonemic hearing is a prerequisite for teaching children the ability to perform sound analysis of words. Pitch hearing is the ability to perceive and recognize pitch changes in the voice, to feel the emotional coloring of speech. Perception of the rate of speech and loudness of the voice - the ability to hear the speed and loudness of speech utterance. Rhythmic hearing is the ability to hear and correctly repeat the rhythmic pattern of a word, to determine the place of stress in it. A well-formed speech hearing makes it possible to clearly, clearly and correctly pronounce all the sounds

of the native language, ensures the correct regulation of the volume of pronunciation of words, a moderate rate of speech, and intonation expressiveness.

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